

DATA SPACE FOR
SMART AND SUSTAINABLE
CITIES AND COMMUNITIES

An Initiative Overview

LIVING-IN.EU

Presented by
Sophie Meszaros

Funded by
the European Union

CitCom.ai TEF

Data spaces

Data platforms

DATA SPACE FOR
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Data Space for Tourism Website

Overview of Engaged Communities

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CSA

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Sign the declaration @
www.living-in.eu/declaration

Join the Stakeholder Forum
sophie@oascities.org

LIVING-IN.LEU

Cities & Communities
(Signatories)

Industry
(Supporters)

Capacity Building

Financial

Legal

Monitoring & Measuring

Technical

MIMs Plus

Subgroups

Technical Blueprint

[Open DEI framework](#)

Example of the community's work on the MIMs

Cities as enablers of the data economy

different types of data and interests need to converge and be harmonised to provide a common goal: better quality of life in cities for people and businesses

- City as data/service provider/consumer
- Decision-making for both citizens and managers

Challenges

- break the silos
- avoid vendor lock-in
- business model
- interoperability
- portability

Across sectors & domains...

reservations estimation of the hotels

number of airport passengers

better the public transportation of the city in certain days

... cross-domain data spaces

DS4SSCC - An Initiative Overview

Oct, 2022 - Oct, 2023

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DS4SSCC - An Initiative Overview

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Stakeholder Forum

Workshops, surveys, interviews

governance scheme, catalogue of specifications, roadmap, capacity building
(WP2, 3, 4, 5)

Activities

Stakeholder Forum Workshops

7 events

Expression of Interest Form

36 Responses

Survey

85 Responses

Interviews

22 Interviews

Identification of use-cases

Use case 1: Optimising traffic management to reduce pollution

Alignment with Green Deal Objectives:

- Accelerating the shift to smart & sustainable mobility
- Zero-pollution ambition for a toxic-free environment

Led by Amsterdam and Lisbon

Use case 2: Management of energy flows in a city/community-specific context

Alignment with Green Deal Objectives:

- Supplying clean, affordable, and secure energy
- Leave no-one behind (Just Transition)

Led by Barcelona

...and more

Florence	A unique platform combining dashboards on mobility, environment, resilience, social energy and policy making to manage the city.
Flanders	Flanders Smart Data Space Data Integration for Smart Mobility Flanders Water Dataspace
Helsinki	Heating demand prediction based on 3D city models, The simulation environment SimStadt uses 3D city models in CityGML format to perform urban analysis, like solar potential-, enviromental-analysis, or heating demand calculations.
Eindhoven	At the heart of this transition will be Urban Digital Twinning: creating digital versions of the city that visualizes the high level of complexity and the many interdependencies in a tangible way. Digital Twinning can be used to build different scenarios for future plans. It supports evidence-based decision making and empowering citizens.
Barcelona, Göteborg, Amersfoort	SCOREwater develops and tests three large-scale demonstrations cases for collecting, computing and presenting various data tailored to needs of our stakeholders. In Barcelona we initiate a new domain “sewage sociology” mining biomarkers of community-wide lifestyle habits from sewage. In Amersfoort we develop new water monitoring techniques and data-adaptive storm water treatment and apply to water resource protection and legal compliance for construction projects within the Göteborg-case. We enhance resilience against flooding by sensing and hydrological modelling coupled to urban water engineering. We will identify best practices for developing and using the digital services, thus addressing water stakeholders beyond the project partners. The project will also develop technologies to increase public engagement in water management.
Amsterdam	IDEA predictive mobility based on floating car data
Slovenia	Farm2Fork: connect schools to suppliers

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Questions we ask ...

Who are the key partners?

What is your motivation/objective?

What are the costs?

How do you distribute the costs?

Who can access?

What is the decision-making process?

What standards/formats are used?

What data is exchanged? What are the data sources used?

What technical concepts or models need to be in place for the data exchange?

What technical infrastructure is needed for the data exchange?

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Date, Location	Event	Event objective
January 16th 2023, Brussels (BE) (Hybrid format)	1st workshop	Work-in-progress presentation
		Inputs/feedback collection on the DS4SSCC activities and expected results
02nd March (10am-12pm), online	2nd workshop	Presentation of DS4SSCC work-in-progress
		Collection of insights on the data governance scheme development, priority data sets & the blueprint
12th April (10am-12pm), online	3rd workshop	Presentation of DS4SSCC work-in-progress and collection of insights on the WP2, WP3, WP4 project activities and outcomes
03rd May (10am-12pm), online	4th workshop	Presentation of DS4SSCC work-in progress, collection of feedback on the project activities and validation of the catalogue of specification
07th of June (10am-12pm),online	5th workshop	Presentation of DS4SSCC work-in progress, sneak peek into the governance scheme, Capacity Building Exercise by ENoLL
05th July (10am-12pm), online	6th workshop	First validation of the architecture- WP4
06th September (10am-12pm), online	7th workshop	Final validation of data governance scheme and the roadmap
September 2023 (10am-12pm), Barcelona (ES)	Event on Data Spaces at the Open Living Labs Days	Presentation and promotion of the DS4SSCC results
		Connection with sister and related projects
		Panel discussion

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www.ds4sscc.eu

Narrative document
Online navigable catalogue
Whitepaper for public
Capacity building
Newsletter

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General Announcements

- Invited to prepare the Deployment Call
- Deployment Project kickoff October 2023
- Calls to be launched in January 2024
(3 months to apply)

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Thank you for listening

Any comments, questions or suggestions?

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Follow us on LinkedIn & Twitter

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